

SCREENING OF CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES IN PERSONS OVER 40 YEARS OF AGE

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Abstract. Strokes are caused by blockages in the carotid arteries in the neck that carry blood to the brain. When the blood flow is restricted to the brain, symptoms can occur that may lead to disability, or even death. Stroke is the leading cause of long-term adult disability and the fifth leading cause of death in the world. In many economically developed countries, over the past decades, it has been possible to significantly reduce the mortality rate from CVD, which is associated both with the introduction of modern methods of early diagnosis and treatment of CVD, and with the strengthening of preventive measures in health care. For our country, the organization of work on the prevention of CVD is also of paramount importance and is recognized as an important state task by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of August 30, 2018 PP-3925 "On measures to improve neurological care for the population" and of December 18, 2018 PP-4063 "On measures to prevent non-communicable diseases, support a healthy lifestyle and increase the level of physical activity of the population". In 2012, in Uzbekistan, in the structure of the population seeking medical care due to DBS, patients with CVD accounted for 21.6%. As practice shows, often in patients of working age, the clinical symptoms of CVD are poorly expressed, as a result of which patients do not seek medical help in a timely manner. Data from domestic epidemiological studies have shown that about 40% of patients with the presence of CVD did not know about their disease. Many patients with chronic forms of CVD are also unaware of the presence of the disease and often come to the attention of medical professionals only at the stage of development of acute stroke.

Keywords: cerebrovascular diseases (CVD), diseases of the blood system (DBS), Chronic Brain Ischemia (ChBI), cardiovascular diseases (CVD), body mass index (BMI).

Objective: to study the prevalence of CVD and their main risk factors in male and female open populations over 40 years of age in various regions of Uzbekistan and to develop scientifically based preventive and diagnostic measures to improve the quality of diagnosis, prevention and treatment of cerebrovascular diseases in the region, as well as to improve the organization of medical care for patients with CVD based on the stages of its provision.

Materials and methods of research: 1813 patients aged 40 and over were examined in various medical institutions who turned to a local therapist. The examined patients were given collection of complaints, anamnesis, examination of neurological status. In order to screen the central nervous system, BMI was measured, blood pressure was checked with both hands using the method Korsakov, auscultation of the carotid arteries from the place of their bifurcation. A Mini COG test was used to determine cognitive impairment. Also, for the definition of ChBI was used Fedin's scale and questionnaire. The following biochemical research methods were also used: express method of determining the level of cholesterol and sugar in the blood.

Results of research: The results of the observations showed: low risk of CVD in 24% of the examined, medium - in 62%, high - in 14% of the examined patients. By age categories in patients aged 40-50 years, the risk of developing CVD was shown low risk 27% and medium risk 73%. At the age of 50-60 years, the risk of developing CVD is low 50%, average 42% and 8% high. The rates after 60 years of age in CVD patients showed 39% low risk, 38% moderate risk, and 23% high risk.

Conclusion. The results showed that patients with high blood pressure have a high risk of developing CVD. Being overweight and having high blood cholesterol increases the occurrence of CVD. The use of a unified questionnaire is effective in the survey patients for early detection of CVD. The use of this screening serves as an early detection of CVD with subsequent prevention and treatment.

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